

EXPERIENCE AND MEANING OBTAINED BY BULLYING VICTIM IN SMAN 3 SALATIGA, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

The main aim of this research is to know the experience obtained by bullying victim in SMAN 3 Salatiga, as well the meaning of bullying for victim based on their own experience. This research is a qualitative research using a phenomenology approach. This research is conducted in SMAN 3 Salatiga, Salatiga city, central Java, Indonesia. Research implementation began in November 2017 until February 2018. The participants are ten students (victims of bullying). They consist of five students of first-grade senior high school and five students of second-grade senior high school. The techniques of collecting data used were interview and documentation. Analyzing qualitative data used software Nvivo. Respondents obtained bullying experiences in both physical and verbal way. Bullying executant comes from family and school environment. The victims' reaction and the impact got toward bullying activity are various enough. For the victims, bullying activities give a negative impact on both their psychological and physical, such as creating the traumatic effect and the desire to avoid themselves from association and environment.

Keywords: the form of bullying, bullying experience, the meaning of bullying

1. Introduction

Bullying becomes the main reason for students who got bullying activity feeling uncomfortable attending school because bullying is one of the violence and aggressive

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action occurring in school (Mishna, Khoury-Kassabri, Gadalla, & Daciuk, 2012; Trisnani & Wardhani, 2016). Generally, bullying can be verbal and physical. The most bullying activity occurred in a school environment which didn't even realize by the executant is verbal bullying, such as calling unreal name like fatty, skinny, etc. The executant often assumes the verbal bullying as a joke, they didn't even realize that the victim of their verbal bullying can feel uncomfortable for that "joke".

Based on the result of a study conducted by the expert of bullying intervention, Dr Ami Huneck, it is obtained that 10-60 percent of students in Indonesia reporting that they got ridicule, exclusion, blow, and kick once a week (Wiyani, 2012). Bullying activity most occur on adolescent stage because it's transition stage from children to adult which is 13 to 18 years old.

The age of 12 to 14 years old is categorized as pre puberty stage while the age of 15 to 18 years old is categorized as a puberty stage (Azizah, 2013). Junior and senior high school year are immature stages of students, they will pass their growth stage with a certain difficulty level; on senior high school level, developing new thinking students as well develop the maturity of their behaviour are the characteristics of the adolescent by the age of 15 to 18 years old (Kusdiyati & Halimah, 2011; Unayah & Sabarisman, 2016). On this stage, students' psychic condition is very unstable, therefore lead them to do bullying activity to their friends as a caused by their unstable emotion. However, based on the study conducted by Fithria and Auli (2016) showed that there is a significant relationship between school and bullying activity, school tends to assume that bullying is not a big issue and they prefer to ignore the bullying activity. Therefore it makes the bullying executant feels stronger to intimidate the bullying victims.

Schools tend to be passive to pay attention and handle the bullying case. Therefore the victims didn't report the bullying case because they feel that school couldn't protect them. Besides that, the study conducted by Veenstra, Lindenberg, Huitsing, Sainio, and Salmivalli (2014) showed that the result tends to be same, where students assume that teacher didn't give the effort to reduce bullying activity and the weakest students tend to get the highest intimidation level. The study conducted by Mishna, Saini, and Solomon (2009) confirms this case, that teacher assumes that physical bullying is more seriously than verbal bullying. Therefore they didn't take serious action to handle the verbal bullying activity.

Bullying becomes stronger when the group commits it. There is a tendency if the bullying activity will increase if it is reinforced by the group (peer group), and it is committed toward the outside of the group (Mishna, 2003; Mishna et al., 2012; Pozzoli & Gini, 2010). It's still memorized about the most familiar bullying case about the phenomenon of a female gang which called Nero Gang. The bullying case committed by this gang occurred in Pati city, central Java. The group members of this gang committed violence toward their junior in school. They often determine the bullying activity to those who they don't like. This action reaped so the many critics from the different side, especially in other students' circle from other cities.

In 2017, bullying activity by students also occurred in Thamrin city, the centre of Jakarta. The case happens because the victim and the executor mocked each other. It caused the executor to feel hurt and asked the victim to meet her in Thamrin city, and the victim was grabbed her hair and hit. Because of many other students watching, the case was recorded and became viral in social media (Kompas.com, 17 Juli 2017).

Moreover, bullying case also occurred in one of the famous university in Jakarta. The victim has had abuse and caused he couldn't walk, and he is often abused and mocked by the executor. The victim confesses that he had bullying activity since in the first semester until the third semester. The bullying activity got in many ways, such as locking him in the classroom, calling him in unreal name and taking the victim's own, etc. (Liputan6.com, 20 Juli 2017).

All of the cases above prove that bullying activity not only occurs in junior high school level but also at the university level. Based on the study conducted by Gower, McMorris, and Eisenberg (2015) state that school with the nickname of favourite school, excellent school or the highest accreditation have the lower level of bullying activity than school in margin area or with lower accreditation. However, it is very different in Indonesia, some of the favourite schools committed bullying activity and caused the executor to get kick out of the school. One of them occurred in one of the schools in Cinere, Jakarta. Five students committed violence toward their new junior (Kompas.com, 31 Maret 2012).

In SMAN 3 Salatiga, as one of the favourite school in this city also registered bullying activity. Based on the interview on background study with the victim, said that she/he often got bullying by her/his classmate such as verbal and physics, she/he cried and said that she/he didn't feel strong and thinking about committed suicide. Physical bullying is the most dangerous bullying because it can danger the victim, even can lose their life (Fithria & Auli, 2016).

The other victims, B and C told that they often got verbal bullying like calling their name in an unpleasant way. According to them, the executor called their unreal name is a joke, unknowing that the victim felt unpleasant with that name. The victims have no courage and power to tell the bullying activity they got to teacher or school because they feel afraid to the executor and assuming that school didn't give any effect to stop the bullying they got. Besides, based on the interview conducted by the research with counselling guidance teacher about bullying case in school, teachers assume that verbal bullying often occurring is only a joke between students. Therefore teachers are didn't care enough with the executor.

Many sides strive to decrease the bullying activity occurring in school. The social ministry acquires direct complaint medium and also complaint calling to facilitate violent victim. Even Salatiga as one of the small city in Indonesia strives several ways to decrease bullying activity in the education world. The head of Bapermaster Salatiga, Afif Zufroningdyah state that bullying case in Salatiga has increased from 2015 to 2016, from 25 reports became 32 reports until November 2016 (Kabarsalatiganews.com, December 2016). This number of cases is estimated will increase every year because many students didn't report the bullying case they got in school. Kasat Binmas Polres

Salatiga, AKP Kristyastuti, give an appeal and emphasis when became ceremony inspector in one of vocational high school in Salatiga about bullying and effort to anticipate to avoid bullying case. (Tribratanews.jateng.polri.go.id, 31 Juli 2017).

From various facts that have been told can be a description of the educational situation at present. School is the second place after the family which should function for students to be able to get an education and deep the experience. However, there are still many bullying cases which are far from educational goal in school, by understanding how bullying victim represented bullying action they have as well their responses can make it easy for every side to minimize bullying action in school and help to rehabilitate psychological condition of bullying victims. Swearer and Hymel (2015) state that the effort of prevention and effective intervention of intimidation must consider the complexity of human experience, handling individual characteristic and involvement history in intimidation factor, risk and protection, and content where intimidation occurs to create a harmonious life. Therefore, it is essential to research bullying experience and meaning for victims in SMAN 3 Salatiga. The main aim of this research is to know the experience obtained by bullying victim in SMAN 3 Salatiga as well as bullying meaning for the victim based on the experience they have.

2. Research Method

2.1 Research Type

This research is qualitative research which used phenomenology approach. Qualitative research used the natural background to interpret the phenomenon by using various method (Moleong, 2013). Phenomenology is systematically method which depends on the experience as well as defining the definition (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

2.2 Time and Research Location

This research is conducted in SMAN 3 Salatiga in Kartini Street no. 34 Salatiga, Sidorejo, Salatiga City, Center of Java Indonesia. The study is implemented from November 2017 to February 2018.

2.3 Sample and Data Resources

Collecting data was conducted by using various sources and ways. Primary data source in this research is students (bullying victims) and Counseling Guidance teacher of SMAN 3 Salatiga. Verbal sentences and subject action observed and interviewed are main data sources (Moleong, 2013). The number of participants in this research is about ten students (victims of bullying) which include five students from first grade and five students from second grade. The reason for taking first and second-grade students is because they have applied the 2013 curriculum and they are classmate with the same students from first grade.

The source of secondary data is the second data source which cannot be ignored. Secondary information is obtained by indirect giving data on data collecting, such as by

document and other people (Sugiyono, 2008). In this research, the source of secondary data comes from online media and other relevant research.

2.4 The Technique of Collecting Data

Generally, in qualitative research use four kinds of technique of collecting data, such as interview, observation, documentation and mixing or triangulation (Sugiyono, 2008). This research uses several techniques for collecting data such as interview and documentation.

In this research, the technique of collecting data used is interview, observation and documentation. The instrument needed is clues of interview and observation. The clues including demographics of the informant, the knowledge about bullying (definition of bullying, the executor, the reason, and kind of bullying) and the experience of bullying (bullying experience, feeling of the victims, and interaction with friends and the meaning of bullying). The clues of observation guidelines include kinds of bullying (verbal and physical bullying) and environments responses (active and passive).

The informant is determined by using the technique of snowball sampling, such as determining sample which starts from little become many. The informant is obtained based on the recommendation from the previous informant by digging the information relating to the research topic. Searching the informant is done after the number expected is filled or information obtained is assumed adequate.

2.5 The technique of Analyzing Data

In this research, to support the validity of data, the researcher used triangulation. Triangulation is a technique to know whether the data is valid or not by using another source of data (Moleong, 2013). Triangulation can be interpreted as checking data by using various sources, ways and times. Therefore, triangulation can be differentiated as three kinds, such as source, technique and time of triangulation

The technique of analyzing data in this research is conducted before, during and after the research. Bogan & Biklen explain if the data analyzing is an effort of work by data, organizing data, sorting the data to be the unit which can be managed, synthesizing, searching and finding the pattern, defining the important and what should be learnt, as well determining what can be told to other (Moleong, 2013). The researcher used software Nvivo to help to analyze qualitative data obtained in the field.

3. Research Result and Discussion

3.1 Kinds of Bullying

Bullying action had by students who are participants in this research is including physical violence, verbal bullying. Based on the analyzing result toward bullying experience by students, verbal bullying is the most bullying action occurring in school. The result of the analysis from interviewing transcription, frequency of physical and verbal bullying are presented in the table below.

Table 1: Kinds of Participants' Experiences Having Bullying Action

Physical Bullying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Getting hit in the body - Getting hit by ball in the head - Joking about body tall - Blocked her/his way - Kicking, pushing, and blocked
Bullying experience	
Verbal Bullying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ridicule - Mocking - Calling name in a bad way - Scorn - Yell, nagging and threat - Excessive joking

The table below present kinds of physical and verbal bullying had by participants.

Table 2: Kinds Of Physical And Verbal Bullying Had By Participants

Participants	Physical Bullying	Verbal Bullying
A		Insinuated by classmate through comment or status update in social media Bullied through uncomfortable words
	Hit by parents and family member every time she/he is assumed making mistakes	Scolded and reviled because of deciding to convert their religion
B	Calling her/his name as "foreigner (Bule)" because of her/his appearance looks like a foreigner.	Mocked by calling "cheap" and "can be bought by male", "can be taken home."
	Shunned physically in a group activity	Invective from parents and family The insinuation from friends because of their broken home family
D		Mockery and calling her/his name as four feet animal
MJ	Piloted his sport pants Banged on his/her table when she/he take a rest	I have insinuated because of their family's past.
M		Calling her/his name by "bucktoothed" because she/he has rabbit teeth Ridicule about "bucktoothed" through social media like Instagram and Facebook by the caption "yang giginya itu lho, yang giginya..."
	Friends hide Her/his things before the exam	Ridicule which caused victim cried
N	Her/his wheelchair is smeared by type ex Rejected and shunned in group formation in class	Insinuation Called his/her name with mockery

	Stoned by ball in his head	
MS	Stoned by ball in his head	Insinuation Called his/her name with mockery
S		Ridicule Called his/her name with mockery
L		Insinuation Called his/her name with mockery
T		Insinuation and mockery by called her as friend's boyfriend usurper Threat from counselling and guidance teacher that his/her parents will be called if she/he still make a mistake Called her as relationship destroyed

Table 3: Coding Matrix of Kinds of Bullying Had by Participants

Participants	Physical Bullying	Verbal Bullying
A	1	7
B	4	2
D	1	1
MJ	0	0
M	2	0
N	7	7
MS	0	4
S	0	5
L	0	3
T	0	5

Figure 1: Number and Type of Bullying Experienced by Each Respondent

Based on the Table 1,2 and 3, it shows that there are participants that have ever gotten only physical bullying, verbal bullying, and moreover both of them (verbal and physical bullying). Based on interview result from students, the most bullying action

they have gotten is verbal bullying such as ridicule, mockery, satire, invective, threat and calling the victim's name which has humiliated connotation.

Verbal bullying is mocking by using uncomfortable words for victims. The victims said that they got bullying experience in verbal bullying. Verbal bullying that they have ever have are insinuation sentences, mockery, yell, called her/his name by harassing, mockery, or joke which caused painful for victims.

Various kinds of bullying are having by participants in this research, both of in the past and present. One of the participants, B, she is second-grade senior high school, told her story that she got physical bullying continuously both the school environment and family environment.

Generally, bullying consists of two kinds, such as verbal and non-verbal bullying (physical). This is similar with the statement of Astuti (2008) who classified bullying into two kinds of bullying such as verbal and non-verbal. However, several people classify bullying by different terms but have the same meaning. Based on several kinds of bullying, it can be known that bullying has various types which all of them have negative behaviour which cannot be continued. In several schools, the widest bullying occurs verbal bullying which is assumed as joke by the executor. However, in several cases, verbal bullying which is often done usually accompanied by physical bullying by the executor toward the victim.

3.2 Bullying Executor

Bullying action having by the bullying victims occur in their daily interaction, both school and family environment. Several participants said that they became the bullying victims mainly when they have interaction with friends in school, member of the family at the home and another environment. Based on the interview result, it is found that the executors are victim's friends both in school and family environment. The executor in school, especially the victim's classmate, in many cases is the victim's close friend. Moreover, the executor also from another class, especially their senior.

Several bullying victims in SMAN 3 Salatiga said that they got bullying not only when they are in school but also their family environment. In this case, students' harmony life also has significant correlation toward bullying action they got in their family environment. One of the participants in this research got bullying action from his/her parent and her/his other family members because of their family background which is not harmony.

3.3 Feeling and Reaction toward Bullying

Bullying action in school caused many problems which are not known by many other people. Bullying can give an unsafety and uncomfortable feeling for the victim when they are in school. (Surilena, 2016) state that bullying victim will feel lonely, difficult in adaptation, having insomnia, excessive anxiety. Based on the interview result, feeling and reaction toward bullying such as crying, ignoring and silence, as well as fighting and clarifying.

3.4 The Meaning of Bullying

The experience of getting bullying gives various meanings toward bullying victims in SMAN 3 Salatiga. Meaning toward bullying for each bullying victim is influenced by how the effect of bullying toward the victim. Based on interview result, the effect of bullying felt by the victims both in school and family environment are offence, they are lazy to study and coming school, skipping class, keeping distance in group activity, tends to be alone, blame his/herself, desire to commit suicide, having motivation to have more prestige.

Bullying action had by the bullying victims occur in daily interaction both school and family environment. Several participants said that they became bullying victim mainly when they have interaction with friends in school, member of the family and other environments. Based on the interview result, it is found that the executor is the victim's friend in both school and family environment. This founding is parallel with Simbolon (2012) opinion, states if bullying can occur because of internal and external factors. Another opinion from Yusuf and Fahrudin (2012), states that family factor, school and media are the main factors that caused someone to become bullying executor and the bullying victim.

Parents' parenting toward children influences somebody to become bullying executor and bullying victim. Parents applying physical discipline tends to deny and hostile, not having good solving problem, as well teach children to revenge if there are a contra and provocation tends to shape the bully behaviour toward children, while authoritarian parenting can shape children's fear, therefore, they cannot interact well in environment which caused them to become the bullying victims. Weak supervision and school management make students are free to commit bullying in school because there is no punishment.

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The physical and psychological effect is felt by a bullying victim. Trisnani and Wardhani (2016) state that bullying can give the effect toward victim's physic and psychology. The physical effect got by the victim can be painful in their body because of bruises or wound in their body. Psychology effect can be like they feel lazy to go to school, depression, insomnia, nervous, fear, angry, hold grudges, uncomfortable, feel threatened, sad and cannot interact well. Heydenberk and Heydenberk (2017) add by the state if bullying gives negative effect for mentally health, physic, social relationship, cognitive function and productivity, such as increasing depression risk, school failure, growth problem related to the long-term depression. Besides that, bullying raises shameless, anxiety for the victim; therefore they feel difficult in interaction which caused problem for victim both in present and future.

Bullying always gives a negative effect on the victim. Caruso Jr (2015) state that the worst effect of bullying for the victim is the desire to commit suicide because of feeling depression and have no struggle to live. The various negative effect can be minimized, even removed to manifest a bright future for victims. Therefore, they can interact well with others and have a harmonious life.

Figure 2. Comparison of the Number of Physical Bullying and Verbal Bullying

4. Conclusion

The bullying victims of SMAN 3 Salatiga got bullying experience in physical and verbal bullying. Physical bullying experience including the hit, kick, throw, push, physical joke such as mock because of the physical appearance of the victim. Verbal bullying experience consists of insinuation, invective, mockery, threat, ridicule, mockery about the nickname, yell, joke with humiliating words. Bullying action had by victims majority occur in school, but some students have bullying action both in school and family environment.

Bullying executor in a school environment are victims' classmate and other class, they can be male or female both individually and in the group. Bullying executor in a family environment is students' parents and another family member as an effect of disharmony life.

The reason why the victims got bullying action can be various for every victim, such as different physical appearance, misunderstanding in interaction with friends, moreover it is caused by the character of executor which wants to oppress.

Victims' reaction toward bullying action they got such as (1) silence; (2) fighting and clarification; (3) crying and blame her/himself. The effect of getting bullying action by the victims including of (1) offence (2) feeling lazy to study, coming to school and skipping class which caused victim's prestige to become low; (3) kept distance in group activity; (4) tends to be alone; (5) blame her/himself; (6) arise the desire to commit suicide.

The meaning of bullying for victims gives them negative effect psychologically and physically, raise traumatic feeling and the desire to keep distance with relationship and environment which caused bullying action.

References

- Astuti, P. R. (2008). *Meredam Bullying: 3 cara efektif menanggulangi kekerasan pada anak*. Jakarta: Grasindo.
- Azizah, A. (2013). *Kebahagiaan dan Permasalahan di Usia Remaja(Penggunaan informasi dalam pelayanan Bimbingan Individual)*.
- Caruso Jr, J. (2015). Media Review: Anti-Bullying Websites. *International Journal of Multicultural Education*, 17(3), 128-132.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*: Sage publications.
- Fithria, F., & Auli, R. (2016). Faktor-faktor yang Berhubungan dengan Perilaku Bullying. *Idea Nursing Journal*, 7(3), 9-17.
- Gower, A. L., McMorris, B. J., & Eisenberg, M. E. (2015). School-level contextual predictors of bullying and harassment experiences among adolescents. *Social Science & Medicine*, 147, 47-53.
- Heydenberk, R. A., & Heydenberk, W. R. (2017). Bullying reduction and subjective wellbeing: The benefits of reduced bullying reach far beyond the victim. *International Journal of Wellbeing*, 7(1).
- Kusdiyati, S., & Halimah, L. (2011). *Penyesuaian diri di lingkungan sekolah pada siswa kelas XI SMA pasundan 2 bandung*: Universitas Ahmad Dahlan.
- Mishna, F. (2003). Learning disabilities and bullying: Double jeopardy. *Journal of learning disabilities*, 36(4), 336-347.
- Mishna, F., Khoury-Kassabri, M., Gadalla, T., & Daciuk, J. (2012). Risk factors for involvement in cyber bullying: Victims, bullies and bully-victims. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 34(1), 63-70.
- Mishna, F., Saini, M., & Solomon, S. (2009). Ongoing and online: Children and youth's perceptions of cyber bullying. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 31(12), 1222-1228.
- Moleong, J. (2013). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif. Edisi Revisi*. Bandung: Cetakan ke-28. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Pozzoli, T., & Gini, G. (2010). Active defending and passive bystanding behavior in bullying: The role of personal characteristics and perceived peer pressure. *Journal of abnormal child psychology*, 38(6), 815-827.
- Simbolon, M. (2012). Perilaku bullying pada mahasiswa berasrama. *Jurnal Psikologi*, 39(2), 233-243.
- Sugiyono. (2008). *Metode penelitian pendidikan:(pendekatan kuantitatif, kualitatif dan R & D)*: Alfabeta.

- Surilena. (2016). Perilaku Bullying (Perundungan) pada Anak dan Remaja. *CDK Journal, Vol 43*(No 1), 35-38.
- Swearer, S., & Hymel, S. (2015). Bullying and discrimination in schools: Exploring variations across student subgroups. *School Psychology Review, 44*(4), 504-509.
- Trisnani, R. P., & Wardhani, S. Y. (2016). Perilaku bullying di sekolah. *G-COUNS Jurnal Bimbingan dan Konseling, 1*(1).
- Unayah, N., & Sabarisman, M. (2016). Fenomena kenakalan remaja dan kriminalitas. *Sosio informa, 1*(2).
- Veenstra, R., Lindenberg, S., Huitsing, G., Sainio, M., & Salmivalli, C. (2014). The role of teachers in bullying: The relation between antibullying attitudes, efficacy, and efforts to reduce bullying. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 106*(4), 1135.
- Wiyani, N. A. (2012). Save our children from school bullying. *Jogjakarta: Ar-Ruzz Media*.
- Yusuf, H., & Fahrudin, A. (2012). Perilaku bullying: asesmen multidimensi dan intervensi sosial. *Jurnal Psikologi, 11*(2), 10.

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